

Supplementary Material

Progressing Plastics Circularity: A Review of Mechano-Biocatalytic Approaches for Waste Plastic (Re)valorization

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Supplementary Tables

Table S1. Enzymes involved in polyethylene (PE) degradation. Reaction conditions and effect on specific materials are reported for each enzyme.

Enzyme	Origin	Material	Experimental Conditions	Results	Ref
Alkane hydroxylase	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> E7	LMWPE powder Mw 1.700	Compost, 37°C, 80 days 3.5 g LMWPE blended with 200 g (wet weight) sterilized compost. Bioaugmentation with <i>P. aeruginosa</i> E7	40.8% mineralization	(Jeon & Kim, 2015)
Alkane hydroxylase	<i>Pseudomonas</i> sp. E4	LMWPE ^a Mw 1.700	Compost, 37°C, 80 days, PE 5 wt% of compost. The mixture was inoculated with <i>Pseudomonas</i> sp. E4	28.6% mineralization	(Yoon et al., 2012)
Laccase	<i>Rhodococcus ruber</i>	LDPE film 0.92 g/ cm ³ Mw 191,000 3 cm x 3 cm 0.2 mm thick	50 ml synthetic medium, 20µM Cu ⁺ , 30°C, 30 days 300 mg PE films Bioaugmentation with <i>Rhodococcus ruber</i>	2.5% weight loss	(Santo et al., 2013)

^aLow-Molecular-Weight Polyethylene

Table S2. Enzymes involved in polyethylene terephthalate (PET) degradation. Reaction conditions and effect on specific materials are reported for each enzyme.

Enzyme	Origin	GenBank/ PDB ID	Material	Reaction conditions	Weight loss (%)	Ref.
TfH		ALF04778.1	PET-G			
			Beverage bottle films	55 °C, 0.5 mL 0.1 M Phosphate pH 7, 3 weeks with buffer	54.2	
			$T_g=75$ °C 12 mm diameter	change/enzyme addition		(Müller et al., 2005)
			PET-B	(4-5 mg film/mL reaction)		
			(9-10% crystallinity-BASF, DE)	0.8 nmol enzyme/mg film/week or 16 nmol enzyme/cm ² film/week	13.1	
			$T_g =80$ °C 12 mm diameter			
TfH	<i>Thermobifida fusca</i>	ALF04778.1		65 °C, 1.5 mL 1 M Tris pH 8.5, 10 mM CaCl ₂ , 2 d	13	(Then et al., 2015)
TfCut2			PET-GF* film (Goodfellow, UK) 250 µm thick	2.5 nmol enzyme/mg film or 0.4 nmol enzyme/cm ² film	12.6	
TfCut2 variant (D204C-E253C-D174R)		4CG1	(crystallinity 2.3% by (Wei <i>et al.</i> , 2019))	70 °C, 1.5 mL 0.5 M HEPES pH 8, 2 d (30 mg film/mL reaction)	25	(Then et al., 2016)
			(crystallinity 9.8% by (Barth <i>et al.</i> , 2015))	35 µmol enzyme/mg film or 0.5 mmol enzyme/cm ² film		
TfCut2 expressed in <i>Bacillus megaterium</i>				70 °C, 1.8 mL Phosphate pH 8, 5 d (25 mg film/mL reaction)	97	

				0.03 nmol enzyme/mg film or 1 nmol enzyme/cm ² film		
			PET-CP, post- consumer Carton Pack (Carton Pack Srl, Rutigliano, Italy)	70 °C, 1.8 mL Phosphate pH 8, 7 d (17 mg film/mL reaction)	23.9-56.6	(Wei et al., 2019)
			Crystallinity 4-6%	0.05 nmol enzyme/mg film or 1 nmol enzyme/cm ² film		
			PET-AP, post- consumer Agripack (Groupe Guillin, Ormas, France)	70 °C, 1.8 mL 1 M Phosphate pH 8, 7 d (15 mg film/mL reaction)	8.2-50.5	
			Crystallinity 4-6%	0.04 nmol enzyme/mg film or 1 nmol enzyme/cm ² film		
				65 °C, 0.5 mL 0.15 M Bicine pH 9, 10 mM CaCl ₂ , 2 d		
TfCut2			Low crystallinity PET sheets (NOACRYSTAL- V)	(15 mg film/mL reaction)	30	(Furuka wa et al., 2019)
			200 µm thick			
			3-5% crystallinity	65 °C, 1 mL 0.15 M Bicine pH 9, 10 mM CaCl ₂ , 1.25 d		
TfCut2 variant (G62A/F209A)			Coated with C ₁₂ - N(CH ₃) ₃ ⁺ surfactant	(7.5 mg film/mL reaction)	100	
				0.13 nmol enzyme/mg film or 1.7 nmol enzyme/cm ² film		
LCC	Uncultured bacterium	4EB0	PET film from plastic package	50 °C, 1 mL 0.5 M Tris pH 8, 1 d (20-25 mg film/mL reaction)	6.5	(Sulaim an et al., 2012)
				8 pmol enzyme/mg film or 3.6 nmol enzyme/cm ² film		

			PET-GF* film (Goodfellow, UK)	70 °C, 3 mL 0.5 M HEPES pH 8, 2 d	95	(Shirke et al., 2018)
LCC-glycosylated			250 µm thick crystallinity 7%	(30 mg film/mL reaction) 3 mmol enzyme/cm ² film	95	
Cut190*	<i>Saccharomonospora viridis</i>	4WFK	PET-S from package 600 µm thick	63 °C, 1 mL 0.1 M Tris pH 8.2, 50 mM CaCl ₂ , 24% glycerol, 3 d	27	(Kawai et al., 2014)
			PET-GF* film (Goodfellow, UK)	(20-25 mg film/mL reaction)	14	
			250 µm thick	11 nmol enzyme/mg film		
			$T_g=76\text{ °C}$			
HiC	<i>Humicola insolens</i>	4OYY	PET-GF* film (Goodfellow, UK)	70 °C, 3 mL 1 M Tris pH 7.5, 10% glycerol, 4 d	97	(Ronkvist et al., 2009)
			250 µm thick (crystallinity 7%)	13 nmol enzyme/ cm ² film		
			$T_g=75\text{ °C}$			

^a Enzyme concentration per film area is calculated considering that both sides of the film are accessible to the enzyme

Table S3. Enzymes involved in polystyrene (PS) degradation. Reaction conditions and effect on specific materials are reported for each enzyme.

Enzyme	Origin	Material	Experimental Conditions	Results	Ref
Hydroquinone Peroxidase	<i>Azotobacter beijerinckii</i> HM121	Dissolved PS (Aldrich Chem. Co. Inc.) Mn 930,000	0.4 ml of water, 10 mM hydrogen peroxide, 10 mM tetramethylhydroquinone, 100 mM potassium phosphate buffer pH 7.0, 30°C, 10 min 0.4 ml of dichloromethane containing 2 g/L of polystyrene.	Mn reduced to 350 and 1,000	(Nakamiya et al., 1997)
Lacasse	<i>Trametes versicolor</i> Commercial laccase (Sigma-Aldrich)	PSS (Sigma-Aldrich) Mw 70,000 Da	28°C, 5 ml of 50 mM malonate buffer pH 4.5, 0.25 mM of redox mediator 1-HBT, 4 days 1 mg PSS / mL reaction 20 mg protein-10 U (0.5 U / mg protein)	Mn reduced to 56,000 Da	(Krueger et al., 2015)

Table S4. Enzymes involved in polyurethane (PU) degradation. Reaction conditions and effect on specific materials are reported for each enzyme.

Enzyme	Origin	GeneBank/ PDB ID	Material	Experimental Conditions	Results	Ref
PU esterase	<i>Comamonas acidovorans</i> TB-35 (<i>Delftia acidovorans</i>)	AB009606.1/ Q9WX47	Polyester PU (poly(diethylene glycol adipate) and 2,4 TDI)	PU blocks (4x4x1 mm) incubated with cell free extract of transformed <i>E. coli</i> for 48 h at 30°C	50 µmol/ mg protein/ 48 h diethylene glycol, adipic acid, trimethylol propane and 2,4-diaminotoluene released	(Nomura et al., 1998)
Polyurathenase lipase A (PulA)	<i>Pseudomonas fluorescens</i>	AF144089.1/ Q9LAB9	Impranil DLN	Impranil in agar plates incubated at 30°C	Clearing halos were observed	(Vega et al., 1999)
Polyurethanase esterase A (PueA)	<i>Pseudomonas chlorapis</i>	AF069748.1/ Q9X3C0	Impranil DLN	Radial diffusion assay with purified enzyme on agar plates with 1.5% v/v Impranil DLN incubated for 6 h at 26°C	Clearing halos were observed	(Stern & Howard, 2000)
Polyurathenase B (PueB)	<i>Pseudomonas chlorapis</i>	AF 188366/ Q9R9H2	Impranil DLN	Rhodamine B agar plates containing 3 g/L of Impranil DLN	Fluorescent halos were observed	(Howard et al., 2001)
LC cutinase	Metagenome	HQ704839/G9 BY57	Polyester Elastollan B85A-10 and Elastollan C85A-10	PU cubes incubated with purified enzyme at 70°C for 200 h	Weight losses of 4.9% and 4.1% for Elastollan B85A-10 and C85A-10 respectively (FTIR)	(Schmidt et al., 2017)
Lipase	<i>Cryptococcus</i> MTCC 5455	AB671329/ Q874E9	Polyester PU (based on poly(diethylene glycol adipate))	Concentrated lipase (1500 U) 96h at 30 °C	96% weight loss with the production of diethylene	(Thirunavukarasu et al., 2015)

and 2,4 TDI)	glycol (DEG)
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Table S5. Enzymes involved in polylactic acid (PLA) degradation. Reaction conditions and effect on specific materials are reported for each enzyme.

Enzyme	Origin	GenBank/ PDB ID	Material	Experimental Conditions	Results	Ref
ABO2449 Esterase	<i>Alcanivorax borkumensis</i>	YP_694169	Solid PLA (Sigma- Aldrich) Mw $1.0-1.8 \times 10^4$	35 °C, 1.0 ml 0.4 M Tris-HCl pH 8.0, 0.1% Plysurf A210G (detergent), 36 h 10-12 mg PLA powder / mL reaction 0.005 g enzyme/g PLA	Up to 90% conversion of PLA into lactic acid monomers and oligomers	(Hajighase mi et al., 2016)
Proteinase K	-	Sigma Aldrich	Poly (L- lactide) PLLA electrospun fiber Mn 2.8×10^5 g* mol^{-1} 2 cm×2 cm, 0.27 mm thick	37 °C, 250 mL 0.05M Tris-HCl pH=8.6, SDS 5 wt.% with respect to PLLA, 9 h Proteinase K 2 µg/mL	80% weight loss	(Zeng et al., 2004)
Alcalase	Porcine liver	Sigma Aldrich (EC 3.1.1.1) d= 1.25 g/mL	PLA fiber (Toray Industries Inc) 0.126 mm thick 30 g/m ² weight	40°C, 25 mL Tris pH 8.0 and 10 mM CaCl ₂ , 21 days 0.02 g PLA/ ml reaction 0.45 g enzyme/ g PLA	1.4% weight loss	(Lee et al., 2014)
Cutinase (PaE)	<i>Pseudozyma antarctica</i> JCM 10317	-	Poly(DL-lactic acid) pellets (Wako Chemicals) Mw 1.3×10^5	30 °C, 50µl 20 mM Tris– HCl, pH 8.8, 24 h 0.004 mg emulsified PLA/ mL reaction 0.2 mg purified enzyme/ g emulsified PLA	50.4% mineralization	(Shinozaki et al., 2013)
Lipase	<i>Candida cylindracea</i>	EC 3.1.1.3	PLA fiber (Toray Industries Inc) 0.126 mm thick	40°C, 25 mL Tris pH 8.0 and 10 mM CaCl ₂ , 21 days 0.02 g PLA/ mL reaction	Below 5% weight loss	(Lee et al., 2014)

30 g/m²
weight

0.45 g enzyme/ g
PLA

Table S6. Enzymes involved in polyhydroxybutyrate (PHB)/PHB-copolymers degradation. Reaction conditions and effect on specific materials are reported for each enzyme.

Enzyme	Origin	GenBank/ PDB ID	Material	Reaction conditions	Weight loss (%)	Ref.	
PHB depolymerase	<i>Alcaligenes faecalis</i>	AAB40611.1	P(3-HB) from <i>Cupriavidus necator</i> (<i>Alcaligenes eutrophus</i>) M_n 281000 Chloroform-casted film, aged for 3 weeks, T_m 177 °C, X_c 62% 10x10x0.07 mm	37 °C, 1 mL 0.1 M K-Phosphate pH 7.4, 19 h (8 mg film/mL reaction) 2 pmol enzyme/mg film or 8 pmol enzyme/cm ² film	22.5	(Abe & Doi, 1999)	
			74% isotactic P[(R,S)HB], M_n 21600 Chloroform-casted film, aged for 3 weeks, T_m 110 °C, X_c 18% 10x10x 0.07mm		55		
			63% isotactic P[(R,S)HB] M_n 21600 Chloroform-casted film, aged for 3 weeks, T_m 64 °C, X_c 12% 10x10x0.07 mm	37 °C, 1 mL 0.1 M K-Phosphate pH 7.4, 5 h (8 mg film/mL reaction) 2 pmol enzyme/mg film or 8 pmol enzyme/cm ² film	42.5		(Kasuya et al., 1996)
			P(3-HB) from <i>Cupriavidus necator</i> , M_n 228000 Chloroform-casted film, aged for 3 weeks, X_c 60% 10x10x0.07 mm		21.3		
			P(4-HB) from <i>Delftia (Comamonas) acidovorans</i> M_n 203000 Chloroform-casted film, aged for 3 weeks, X_c 38% 10x10x0.07 mm	10			

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			<p>P(3-HP), M_n 143000</p> <p>Chloroform-casted film, aged for 3 weeks, X_c 40%</p> <p>10x10x0.07 mm</p>		26.3	
			<p>P(3-HB) from <i>Cupriavidus necator</i> (<i>Alcaligenes eutrophus</i>)</p> <p>M_n 281000</p> <p>Chloroform-casted film, aged for 3 weeks, T_m 176 °C, X_c 62%</p> <p>10x10x0.1 mm</p>	<p>37 °C, 1 mL 0.1 M K-Phosphate</p> <p>pH 7.4, 5 h</p> <p>(14 mg film/mL reaction)</p> <p>1.1 pmol enzyme/mg film or</p> <p>8 pmol enzyme/cm² film</p>	5.7	(Abe et al., 1998)
		<p>P(HB-co-5mol%HV), M_n 91000</p> <p>Chloroform-casted film, aged for 3 weeks, T_m 147 °C, X_c 50%</p> <p>10x10x0.1 mm</p>	60.7			
		<p>P(HB-co-18mol% lactide), M_n 52000</p> <p>Chloroform-casted film, aged for 3 weeks, T_m 124 °C, X_c 35%</p> <p>10x10x0.1 mm</p>	13.6			
PHB depolymerase	<i>Paucimonas (Pseudomonas) lemoignei</i>	5MLY	<p>P(HB-co-10mol%HV)</p> <p>Bacterial origin (Marlborough Biopolymers Ltd, England)</p> <p>M_n 96000</p> <p>Chloroform-casted film, T_m 145 °C, X_c 61%, 25x8x(0.2-0.3) mm</p>	<p>37 °C, 1.5 mL 50 mM Tris-HCl pH 8, 1 mM CaCl₂, 4x20 h</p> <p>25 pmol enzyme/cm² film/20 h</p>	85	(Scandola et al., 1997)
Lipase	Porcine pancreas (Wako chemical Co., Japan)	-	<p>P(3HB-co-98mol%4HB)</p> <p>Chloroform cast films, then hot-pressed aged for >2 weeks</p> <p>5x5x0.05 mm³</p>	<p>37 °C, 3 mL D-PBS pH 7.4, 120 h</p> <p>(1-2 mg film/mL reaction)</p> <p>2.5 pmol enzyme/mg film or 10 pmol enzyme/cm² film</p>	80	(Chuah et al., 2013)

Table S7. Enzymes involved in poly(butylene succinate) (PBS) degradation. Reaction conditions and effect on specific materials are reported for each enzyme.

Enzyme	Origin	Source	Material	Experimental Conditions	Weight loss (%)	Reference
Lipase	<i>Pseudomonas cepacia</i>	Amano Pharmaceutical Co.	PBSL films (97/3 mol%) Mn 4.9×10^4 5mm x 60 mm 0.2 mm thick	50 °C, 7.6 ml 0.1 M $\text{KH}_2\text{PO}_4/\text{KOH}$ pH 6.0, 14 days 0.66 g PBSL / mL reaction 1.88 mg enzyme /g PBSL 0.016 mg enzyme / mm ² PBSL Or 0.471 nmol enzyme / mm ² PBSL	90	(Taniguchi et al., 2002)
Lipase	<i>Pseudomonas</i> sp.	Amano Pharmaceutical Co.	PBSA films Mn 6.4×10^4 1 mm× 1mm piece 0.1 mm thick	37 °C, 50mM phosphate buffer pH 7.0, 10 days 7.5 U enzyme /mm ² PBSA	96	(Tsutsumi et al., 2003)
Purified lipase	<i>Cryptococcus</i> sp.	-	PBS films Mn 6.0×10^4 200 μm thick	30 °C, 10 ml 0.1M phosphate buffer, pH 7.0, 72 h 2.6 mg PBS / mL reaction 0.63 mg protein / mg PBS	100	(Thirunavukarasu et al., 2016)
Lipase	<i>Candida antarctica</i>	Beijing Cliscent Technology Co	PBS films Mn 10.0×10^4 30 mm×10 mm piece 0.5 mm thick	45 °C, 10 ml phosphate buffer, pH 7.0, 26 h 0.3 U/mm ² PBS	90	(Shi et al., 2019)
Lipase	<i>Pseudomonas</i> sp.	Commercial Lipase PS ^R	PBST (90/10 mol %) films Mn 30.0×10^4 30 mm×10 mm piece 0.1 mm thick	37 °C, 3 ml 1 mM phosphate buffer, pH 7.0, 15 days 0.033 mg enzyme/ mL reaction or	95	(Li et al., 2007)

				0.1 µg enzyme/ mm ² PBST		
Cholesterol esterase	<i>Pseudomonas fluorescens</i>	Sigma Aldrich	PBSA films (40/60 mol %) Mn 3.4×10^4	37 °C, 1 ml phosphate buffer pH 7.2, 15 days	15	(Tserki et al., 2006)
			6 mm×6 mm piece 0.15 mm thick			
Cholesterol esterase	<i>Pseudomonas fluorescens</i>	Sigma Aldrich	PBS films Mn 5.95×10^4	37 °C, 1 ml phosphate buffer pH 7.2, 15 days	10	(Tserki et al., 2006)
			6 mm×6 mm piece 0.15 mm thick			
Cutinase	<i>Fusarium solani</i> -		PBS films Mn 15.0-21.0 $\times 10^4$	40 °C, 10 mL 20 mM Tris-HCl pH 8.0, 10 h 20 µg enzyme/mL reaction	100	(Hu et al., 2016)
			30 mm×10 mm 0.1 mm thick	0.33 µg enzyme/ mm ² PBS or 0.014 nmol enzyme/ mm ² PBS		
Cutinase	<i>Fusarium solani</i> -		PBS films Mn 10.0×10^4	37°C, 10 ml phosphate buffer, pH 7.0, 26 h	100	(Shi et al., 2019)
			30 mm×10 mm piece 0.5 mm thick	0.3 U/mm ² PBS		

Table S8. Enzymes involved in polycaprolactone (PCL) degradation. Reaction conditions and effect on specific materials are reported for each enzyme.

Enzyme	Origin	Material	Experimental Conditions	Results	Reference
Lipase	<i>Pseudomonas</i>	PCL synthesized by ring-opening polymerization	27 °C, 15 mL 0.025 M phosphate buffer pH 7.0, 100 h	100% weight loss for all samples	(Gan et al., 1997)
		M _n 12.5 × 10 ⁴	0.66 mg PCL / mL reaction		
		M _n 5.7 × 10 ⁴	0.75 g enzyme/g PCL		
		M _n 2.4 × 10 ⁴	0.0375 mg enzyme/mm ² PCL		
		0.1-0.3 mm thick 10 mm x10 mm film			
Lipase	<i>Mucor miehei</i>	PCL (Sigma–Aldrich) M _n 87,000	40 °C, Toluene 4 mL, H ₂ O 1.5 mL, 24 h 0.07 g PCL/mL reaction 0.1 g enzyme/g PCL	74% M _n reduction	(Pastorino et al., 2004)
Cutinase	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	PCL film (mixing dichloromethane (20%) and ω-caprolactone monomer)	40°C, 2,6 mL Tris pH 8.0, 6 h	100% weight loss	(Ping et al., 2017)
		250 μm thick 1 cm ²	0.011 g PCL/mL reaction 0.012 g enzyme/ g PCL 0.002 mg enzyme / mm ² PCL		
Cutinase	<i>Fusarium solani</i>	PCL film (mixing dichloromethane (20%) and ω-caprolactone monomer)	40°C, 2.6 mL Tris pH 8.0, 6 h	44.3% weight loss	(Ping et al., 2017)
		250 μm thick 1 cm ²	0.011 g PCL/ ml reaction 0.012 g enzyme/ g PCL 0.002 mg enzyme/mm ² PCL		

